

KHALIFA
UNIVERSITY

CMIS 2014

**CONTACT MECHANICS
INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM**

February 3-5, 2014

Elastic frictional contact problem for arbitrary surface shapes and arbitrary 2D loading history: method of memory diagrams

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We present a solution to the frictional contact problem for two elastic bodies subject to an arbitrary loading in 2D. Using Jäger's reduced friction principle, we replace arbitrary surface shapes by an effective axisymmetric system and calculate its hysteretic response via an original method based on an internal memory function.

Introduction

The objective of this study is to solve a frictional contact problem for various contact geometries and general loading histories. The desired solution is the dependency of normal (a) and tangential (b) displacements on the normal (N) and tangential (T) forces, or vice versa. The related challenge is twofold. Firstly, real complex geometries can include multiple contact zones capable of merging and splitting depending on the normal load. Secondly, each of the individual contacts generally contains stick and slip areas which finally results in hysteretic and memory-dependent behaviour; the system's reaction is not instantaneous but depends on the direction of slip. Here we overcome the geometric difficulty with the help of Jäger's reduced friction principle that makes it possible to replace an arbitrary contact geometry by an equivalent system of two axisymmetric bodies. Then the hysteretic behaviour of the equivalent problem is described via the method of memory diagrams that uses, instead of a complex traction distribution in the contact zone, a simple internal functional dependency containing the same memory information. Following changing loading, the internal "memory function" evolves in accordance to the procedure based of the force balance equation written for small increments of the normal and tangential forces.

Assumptions

Here we accept the following assumptions. (1) Loading is in one plane (i.e. in 2D) and quasistatic. (2) Coulomb friction law with μ , friction coefficient, is postulated for contact stresses. (3) $|T| < \mu N$ so that only partial slip is considered; the opposite for quasistatic loading is trivial. (4) Plasticity and adhesion are ignored. (5) All individual contact spots are aligned (have same normals). (6) The normal solution $a=a(N)$ is independent on tangential loading and is known. (7) Contact bodies are equal or, if not, dissimilarity effects are neglected. (8) Jäger's reduced friction principle is valid for a considered geometry (see below).

Jäger's reduced friction principle

Suppose that for an axisymmetric system the normal solution $N=N(c)$, $a=a(c)$ is known (c is the contact radius). Then the Jäger theorem [1] states that the application of a tangential force T will result in tangential displacement b in accordance to

$$T = \mu(N(c) - N(s)), \quad b = \theta\mu(a(c) - a(s)) \quad (1)$$

where s is radius of the boundary between the stick (central, $\rho < s$) and slip (outer, $s < \rho < c$) zones, and $\theta = 1/2(2-\nu)/(1-\nu)$. The same relation holds for the plane geometry [2] with $\theta=1$; more detail on the validity of the principle is given in [3]. This means that, if we accept as a model assumption that the theorem holds for an arbitrary profile, an arbitrary contact system behaves in the same way as an effective axisymmetric contact (Eq. 1) with the same normal

Method of memory diagrams

The contact problem for axisymmetric profiles is geometrically simpler, but the difficulty related to complex memory effects due to stick and slip "competition" remains. Slip always starts at the contact boundary $\rho=c$ and propagates inward. The traction distribution "memorizes" not only current boundary $\rho=s$ between stick and slip, but some previous values of s depending on the loading history. In addition, for changing N , the contact zone $\rho<c$ itself enlarges or shrinks; in particular, if c increases rapidly enough slip does not develop at all. Automating the account for memory effects is a nontrivial problem that we solve here with the help of the Method of Memory Diagrams (MMD).

The MMD is based on a memory function concept introduced in the following way. Define $\eta=N(c=\rho)$ having the sense of a radial coordinate ρ and then memory function $D(\eta)$ (see Figure 1) with the following properties:

$$T = \mu \int_0^N D(\eta) d\eta, \quad b = \theta \mu \int_0^N D(\eta) \frac{da}{dN} \Big|_{N=\eta} d\eta, \quad (2)$$

where $|D(\eta)| \leq 1$ that eventually follows from the Coulomb friction law. The presence of a section $Q=N(c=s) < \eta < N$ on which $D(\eta) = \pm 1$ means the presence of slip of the corresponding sign in the annulus $s < \rho < c$.

Figure 1: Typical memory function

Figure 2: Typical solution to the contact problem

The procedure of updating a memory diagram (Figure 1) is formulated for small force increments ΔN and ΔT . Once ΔN and ΔT are applied, it is required to update $D(\eta)$ according to its definition. Suppose $\Delta N > 0$ i.e. length of the MD increases. If $(1/\mu)|\Delta T/\Delta N| < 1$ then it is possible to satisfy Eq. (1) by updating the MD on the new interval only. If it is not so, the unbalanced part of ΔT should be equilibrated by allowing slip propagating closer to the MD centre $\eta=\rho=0$. Suppose now $\Delta N < 0$ so that shortening of the MD has already released some tangential force. Then again the related unbalanced part of ΔT is equilibrated via slip with the proper sign. In all those cases, Eq. (2) is satisfied, and b can be directly calculated from the MD in an analytical way. A typical solution is illustrated in Figure 2.

Concluding remarks and acknowledgements

The reported version of the MMD is in preparation for publication; the previous one can be found in [4]. These results might be of interest for modelling the contact acoustical nonlinearity, nonlinear NDT applications, or as physic-based boundary conditions for modelling complex systems containing mechanical contacts.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the ANR (project ANL-MEMS 2010 BLAN 923 01) and of the EC (project ALAMSA - FP7-AAT-2012-RTD-1).

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